

Greening the Hotel Industry in Albay in Relation to Social Responsibility for Sustainable Development

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Abstract:- Green hotel practices are one of the environmentally friendly initiatives that aim to reduce the negative impact on the environment by saving energy (for example, by installing energy-efficient appliances and renewable energy programs), reducing water consumption (for example, by installing water-efficient devices and equipment and implementing a linen and towel reuse program), and managing and reducing waste (e.g., by implementing recycling programs and using durable items rather than disposable ones) (Abdou et al., 2020). In the Philippines, the House of Representatives approved House Bill 9061 on second reading. The bill, which was primarily written by the former president and current speaker Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo, aims to encourage all business organizations—domestic and foreign—established and operating under Philippine laws to uphold corporate social responsibility in the conduct of their operations in the nation. (House of Representatives Press Releases, 2022). Hence, the purpose of this research is to know the different green practices of the different hotels in Albay in relation to social responsibility. The study uses a mixed method research design to identify the profile, green practices and challenges encountered by the hotels, while Pearson of Correlation was also used in order to analyze whether there is a significant relationship between the hotel profile and its practices. The analyzed data revealed that The different green practices in terms of: community involvement and development, human resource management, consumer issues protection, fair operating practices, an organizational governance got the same adjectival interpretation of well-practiced. On the other hand, only the variable environmental health and pollution prevention got the adjectival interpretation of practiced. Furthermore, Regarding the number of rooms and the hotel's green practices, the null hypothesis is accepted; therefore, there is no significant relationship. For the number of employees, only the variable environmental health and pollution prevention got a computed t of 2.06 with tabulated t at 5%, which indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant relationship. Lastly, for the years of operation, two of the variables got a rejected null hypothesis and have a significant relationship between the profile and the green practices: human resource management and environmental health and pollution prevention.

Keywords:- Social Science, Sustainable Development, Green Practices, Hotels, Social Responsibility Mixed Method Research Design, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green hotel practices are one of the environmentally friendly initiatives that aim to reduce the negative impact on the environment by saving energy (for example, by installing energy-efficient appliances and renewable energy programs), reducing water consumption (for example, by installing water-efficient devices and equipment and implementing a linen and towel reuse program), and managing and reducing waste (e.g., by implementing recycling programs and using durable items rather than disposable ones) (Abdou et al., 2020)

Teng, Wu, and Liu (2015) say that "green practices" are programs that encourage hotel owners to save water, energy, and solid waste. This helps save money and protect the environment. The group also said what a "green hotel" is a business that is good for the environment and whose managers work hard to set up programs that help protect the environment. For example, many hotels now give guests the option of not having their bed sheets and towels changed every day. This cuts down on the amount of water, electricity, and laundry soap that goes down the drain.

The hotel industry, as one of the key pillars of the tourism sector, is cognizant of its social duty and regards it as a critical component of its reputation. As a result, in order to meet stakeholders' expectations, organizations require new variables and tools. Corporate Social Responsibility establishes a foothold in the target market's thoughts. Companies are utilizing a variety of strategies to raise the value of their intangible assets as a result of increased global competition, a cluttered media landscape, and a lack of brand identity. CSR not only raises brand awareness among consumers, but it also helps potential customers form favourable brand perceptions. Brands must inspire their stakeholders in a socially responsible manner. Corporate Social Responsibility has been included into more company processes to attain the same goals. Nowadays, businesses intentionally employ CSR as a strategy for marketing (Maheswari & Kumar n.d.).

Nonetheless, meeting the expanding wants of hotel visitors has a number of negative consequences, including air and noise pollution, biodiversity loss, trash generation, noncompliance with basic labour laws, and the expansion of prostitution. As a result, a corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a strategy for hospitality organizations to reduce the negative effects of their operations on natural, cultural, and social surroundings (Chan, n.d.). CSR entails organizations taking on

societal duty in addition to their shareholders and customers (Holloway, 2017.).

The goal of ISO 26000 is to aid all kinds of organizations in promoting social responsibility and advancing sustainable development. Such direction is crucial since corporate sustainability and social responsibility (CSSR) are still not well understood. A comprehensive strategic planning process could increase operational effectiveness because many businesses lack a planned approach to CSSR and instead rely on ad hoc methods. (Hahn, 2012)

In the Philippines, the House of Representatives approved House Bill 9061 on second reading. The bill, which was primarily written by the former president and current speaker Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo, aims to encourage all business organizations—domestic and foreign—established and operating under Philippine laws to uphold corporate social responsibility in the conduct of their operations in the nation. The following are examples of CSR-related activities: charitable programs and projects, scientific research, youth and athlete development, cultural or educational promotion, services for veterans and senior citizens, social welfare, environmental sustainability, health development, disaster relief and assistance, socialized and low-cost housing, and CSR activities relating to employee and worker welfare. Section 43 of Batas Pambansa Blg.68, commonly known as the Corporation Code of the Philippines, shall be amended to encourage businesses to participate in CSR. Stock corporations are prohibited by the amendment from holding onto surplus profits that exceed 100% of their paid-in capital stock, with the following exceptions: 1) when justified by clear corporate expansion or for projects and programs related to corporate social responsibility that have been approved by the board of directors; or 2) when the corporation is prohibited from declaring dividends under any loan agreement with any financial institution or creditor, whether local or foreign (House of Representatives Press Releases, 2022).

There are several international findings and studies regarding businesses' green practices. However, there are only few and limited studies in the Philippines that explored those practices and its relationship with the hotel profile. The researcher has not yet encountered research that relates to this topic within Bicol Region specifically in Albay. This study will bridge the gap between green practices of hotels within their locality, Albay. As a result of this study, the researcher will come up with an action plan about hotel green practices to promote or improve social responsibility and sustainable development.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Respondents of the Study

This study used a mixed method approach while using a purposive sampling technique to gather data. The respondents of the study consisted of eight selected DOT accredited hotels within Albay. For each hotel a manager and 4 other employees from different departments who are available and willing to participate in the data gathering procedure were asked to answer the survey questionnaire distributed.

B. Research Instrument

The research instrument is composed of one part. The quantitative part consists of close-ended questions that are both self-administered and guided by the researcher, it is composed of questions based on the ISO 26000 which is the guidance for social responsibility.

C. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the chosen hotel establishments, through a formal letter, to gather significant information. The data gathering started as soon as permission was granted, and all concerned are informed of the research intentions. After gathering sufficient data, the responses were analyzed and statistically assessed.

D. Statistical Treatment

The respondents were asked to determine the green practices of the hotel establishments in Albay of their agreement with each statement in the survey questionnaire to analyze and quantify using the Likert Scale. The collected data are then tabulated and statistically evaluated using the Weighted Mean. Finally, Pearson of Correlation was used to appraise whether there is a significant relationship between the hotel profile and its green practices. A t-test was used, and results were tabulated at 5% to identify whether the null hypothesis (i.e., No significant relationship between the two perspectives) is rejected or accepted.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Profile of the Department of Tourism Accredited Hotels in Albay.

Table 1 demonstrates the profile of the eight (8) hotel respondents. It includes the no. of rooms, number of employees and the years of operation. For the number of rooms, 26 -40 and 25 rooms and below both garnered the highest frequency count of 3 with a percentage of 37.50. While hotel with 71 rooms and above got a frequency of 2 with 25 percentage.

Larger hotel chains are not shifting to a more sustainable model as rapidly as smaller chains, which is not surprising given that some of the green solutions essential to generate sustainability involve substantial upfront expenditures. Moreover, the expense of such a system increases exponentially as the hotel's size increases (Annali, 2022). The number rooms determine the size of a hotel; in this study, most of the respondents are small hotels, therefore, they are expected to engage and promote green practices towards sustainability efficiently and effectively as compared to larger hotels because they can undertake it with lesser costs or expenses.

In terms of employee count, hotels with 16-30 employees received the highest frequency of 3 with a 37.50 percentage, while hotels with 61 or more employees received the lowest frequency of 1 with a 12.50 percentage.

According to Proven Partners (2022), a strong commitment to sustainability can improve community relations, employee morale, and employee retention. A small hotel has fewer employees compared to larger hotels; in this study, the number of employees is determined as it plays an

important role in determining a hotel's sustainability. Employees are likely to stay and work effectively when their hotels promote good relations and morale towards sustainability.

Finally, for the profile, hotels that have been operating for at least 11 years received the highest frequency of 3, with a percentage of 37.50, whereas hotels that have been operating for at least 9 to 10 years, 7 to 8 years, or 4 years and below received the same frequency of 1, with a percentage of 12.50.

Among the hotel respondents, the majority of them are small hotels in terms of room count, which also explains why they have a limited number of employees. On the other hand, even though most of the respondents are small, they have already been operating for quite some time.

The key to managing a profitable hotel is to keep operating costs in check. High operating costs and wasteful practices reduce profit margins and endanger the long-term financial stability and profitability of a property. On the other side, effective cost management sets up your property for success and durability (Darios, 2022).

TABLE I. PROFILE OF THE DEPARTMENT OF TOURISM ACCREDITED HOTELS IN ALBAY

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
a. No of Rooms		
71 rooms and above	2	25
26 -40 rooms	3	37.50
25 rooms and below	3	37.50
Total	8	100
b. No. of Employees		
61 and above	1	12.50
31-45	2	25
16-30	3	37.50
15 and below	2	25
Total	8	100
c. Years of Operation		
11 yrs and above	3	37.50
9 – 10 yrs	1	12.50
7 – 8 yrs	1	12.50
5 – 6 yrs	2	25.50
4 yrs and below	1	12.50
Total	8	100

In this study, the hotels that operates 11 years and above, received the highest frequency. This indicates that these hotels manages their finances responsibly to operate in such a long time. Alongside with these, the longer they operate, the stronger they need to be more cost effective by reducing expenses and wastes through green or sustainable practices towards hotel's financial stability and profitability.

B. Greening Practices of Hotel Accommodation in Albay.

This shows the green practices of the hotels in Albay in terms of community involvement and development, human resource management, consumer issues and protection, fair operating practices, environmental health and pollution prevention, and organization governance. During the process of gathering data, a total of 42 employees are available to fill

out the questionnaire. They were asked to read the statements per indicator and decide to what extent they applied to them.

TABLE 2. GREENING PRACTICES OF HOTEL ACCOMMODATIONS IN ALBAY

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. Community Involvement and Development	3.51	Well-Practiced
2. Human Resource Management	3.59	Well-Practiced
3. Consumer Issues Protection	3.59	Well-Practiced
4. Fair Operating Practices	3.50	Well-Practiced
5. Environmental Health and Pollution Prevention	3.32	Practiced
6. Organizational Governance	3.54	Well-Practiced

Legend: 3.50-4.49 Well Practiced, 2.50- 3.49 Practiced, 1.50 – 2.49 Least Practiced, 1.00 – 1.49 – Not practiced

Based on these results presented (Table 2), The average weighted mean garnered for community involvement and development is 3.51 which is interpreted as well practiced. This result shows that of all the hotel respondents, most of them are encouraging people to do voluntary work for the community. This can be through participation in different CSR activities that benefit the community. According to Bernard & Bianco (2021) both assert that in order to enhance the perception of fairness and incorporate sustainability as an integral part of the hotel experience, hotels must offer incentives to visitors and other stakeholders for participation in various CSR initiatives. For instance, when customers present confirmation of their CSR involvement, hotels may offer drink coupons to on-site or adjacent eateries, room discount coupons, or loyalty points. The researcher's study revealed that community involvement and development practices are well practiced by the hotels or the respondents. In this sense, these hotels can foster good community relations and community's trust through sustainable plans, initiatives and programs towards sustainable development. Moreover, they can promote their green practices and encourage present and target customers to support their hotel while being environmentally responsible.

The garnered weighted mean for human resource management is 3.59 and interpreted as well practiced. According to Choudhary & Datta (2022), green HRM practices start with changing the organization's image to attract environmentally conscious workers, enhancing and developing the staff's environmental competencies by giving them appropriate training and development opportunities, and supporting the development of an eco-friendly culture in the organization for the smooth flow of sustainability initiatives that foster a sense of pride among the workers for their role in the organization.

In this study, Respect that workers have the right to form or join their own groups to look out for their own interest or bargain as a group received the highest with an

interpretation of well practiced. As supported by Choudhary and Datta's statement above, forming and creating groups based on common interest can foster development and opportunities for the organization and paves the way towards pride and sustainability.

The average weighted mean for consumer issues protection was 3.59 and interpreted as well practiced. Consumer rights and safety are crucial in the hospitality sector, claim Makanyeza et al (2021). Consumer rights are central to achieving sustainable development, because, as elucidated by Consumers International, these rights contribute towards a fairer, safer and healthier society, and a more equitable and efficient economy (UNCTAD, 2022). In this study, the hotels stated that they protect their customers' data or information, they only utilize it for marketing and ask for their customers' consent, as supported by the law. Consumer issues protection is well practiced by the respondents which are the hotels. Therefore, it is essential to have a balance between a hotel's business and the rights, interests, and wants of its customers.

Meanwhile, this study revealed that consumer issues protection is well practiced by the respondents; these hotels must continue to participate actively in consumer protection towards sustainable development. Additionally, customers feel protected when a hotel engages in green practices.

In terms of fair operating practices, the average weighted mean garnered was 3.50 interpreted as well practiced. Fair operating practices include avoiding corruption and anticompetitive behavior. It reduces reputational and legal concerns and contributes to the enforcement of existing laws. Fair operating practices refer to an organization's ethical behavior in its relationships with other organizations. These include interactions between organizations and government agencies, as well as relationships between organizations and their partners, suppliers, contractors, customers, rivals, and the associations in which they participate (DFGE, 2022). Lashley (2016) stated that fairness concerns the allocation of resources among individuals, groups, and various interests. Resources include any possession that a community can distribute among its members, including cash and esteem (Fisher & Lovell, 2012, p. 48).

In this study, Put in place policies and practices that encourage respect for property rights and traditional knowledge got the highest weighted mean and interpreted as well practiced, this is supported by the claims stated above. Fair practices should include respect towards the property rights of the stakeholders of the hotels. Furthermore, promote the fair or even allocation of sustainable resources to them to foster anticompetitive behavior and avoid corruption, with these, a hotel is guided towards sustainable development. The government and following the laws promulgated, contributes to stakeholders feeling secured about their rights and resources. These laws help to regulate the hotel operation and practices when it comes to being environmentally sustainable and responsible

The average weighted mean for Environmental Health and Pollution Prevention was 3.32 and interpreted as practiced. Hotels are places where daily, high-intensity human and mechanical activity takes place. This is subject to very strict pollution control standards and will undoubtedly produce various types of pollution. Pollution caused by the hotel industry includes water, air, noise and land pollution (Rajak, 2021). Al-Aomar & Hussain (2017) highlighted that green practices are employed in the suggested framework to decrease waste and expense, minimize pollution, preserve energy, protect natural resources, and lower carbon emissions.

Environmental health and pollution prevention is practiced by the hotels. Specifically, moving towards renewable resources and reduction or prevention of greenhouse emissions are both well practiced by the hotel respondents. The hotel industry contributes to all kinds of pollution that lead to destruction of the environment; thus, the hotels must practice environmentally friendly practices and activities to decrease the negative impact of their operations towards the surroundings. However, the results of this study regarding environmental health and pollution only showed as practiced, hence, utilizing more sustainable and renewable sources of energy, carbon emissions and waste production can be lessened through active engagement to green practices. Engaging in a sustainable, greener, and environmentally responsible actions attracts more customers and other stakeholders, geared towards sustainable development.

The average weighted mean for organizational governance was 3.54 and interpreted as well practiced. In the context of an organization, the social pressures that drive key managers to participate in green initiatives primarily stem from the expectations of various key stakeholders, including suppliers, customers, employees, the government, the general public, and shareholders, according to KUAR et al. (2022).

Finding a good balance between the needs of the organization and the needs of its stakeholders, both now and in the future received the highest mean for organizational governance and is interpreted as well practiced. The needs of stakeholders and the hotel itself should be organized and prioritized for sustainable day-to-day operations as well for future stability of the hotel. Green practices are one of the needs of a hotel to protect and consider the needs of their customers and stakeholder; in this study, organizational governance was well practiced by the hotels.

C. Challenges Encountered by the Hotels on Social Responsibility

This shows the challenges encountered by the hotels in Albay on social responsibility. During the process of gathering data, the same 42 employees answered this part of the questionnaire. They were asked to read the statements and choose all challenges encountered in their establishment of employment.

These are the different challenges encountered by the hotels in Albay on social responsibility. Lack of funds to establish and implement the different green practices ranked 1 with a frequency of 13. Ranked 2 is lack of making plans, goals and targets that show how committed it was to social responsibility with frequency of 9. Lack of suppliers that contribute to sustainable development got the frequency of 8 and was ranked 3. Next at ranked 4, with frequency of 7 was do not take an active role in raising the awareness of organizations with which it works about social responsibility principles and uses. Tie at ranked 5 with frequency of 6, were don't have ways for its stakeholders to talk back and forth with you and difficulty to maintain and upgrade systems to help prevent disruption of services. A triple tie at rank 8 with frequency of 5 are; do not use financial, natural and human resources efficiently, lack of support and training to its employees and representatives to eradicate bribery and corruption and, Don't write down and look into all health and safety problems and incidents in order to reduce or get rid of them. Do not publicly disclose the amount and type of relevant and significant toxic and hazardous materials used and released, and do not provide conditions of all workers that permit to the greatest extent possible, work and work life balance are both rank 10 with a frequency of 4. Lack of full up to date, and correct information about health and safety risk ranked 12 with a frequency of 3 same with lack of steps to make sure that products don't become dangerous because they are handled or stored wrong while in the hand of consumers. Lastly another tie at rank 14 were do not specify the purpose for which personal data are collected, either before or at the time of data collection and lack of information on weights and measures, prices, quality, credit conditions and availability of essential services both of which got frequency of 2.

There are challenges to executing a sustainability program, but they are all surmountable with the proper strategy, tactics, and attitude. The top five sustainability issues are: lack of funding, lack of time, employee push back, prioritization, and greenwashing (Zujewski, 2022). Greening" a business requires an initial investment, but will save money in the long run if you prioritize sustainability. 33% of organizations

surveyed by McKinsey in 2011 about the business of sustainability were incorporating sustainable practices to enhance operational efficiency and save costs, a 19% increase from the previous year. Through sustainable waste management and transparency, clients of the managed service provider Elytus saved over \$11 million over a decade (Maryville University, 2022).

D. Significant relationship between the hotel profile and the hotel green practices.

This research utilized Pearson Correlation in order to appraise the significant relationship between hotel profile and hotel green practices.

Based on the findings presented in Table 3, the computed t of Community Involvement and Development is at 1.73, Human Resource Management at .88, Consumer Issues and Protection at .99, Fair Operating Practices at .32, Environmental Health and Pollution Prevention at .48 and Organizational Governance at 1.34. All variables are obtained a 1.96 tabulated t at 5% which indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. This strongly suggests that there is no significant relationship between hotel's number of room and its green practices.

Larger hotel chains are not shifting to a more sustainable model as rapidly as smaller chains, which is not surprising given that some of the green solutions essential to generate sustainability involve substantial upfront expenditures. Moreover, the expense of such a system increases exponentially as the hotel's size increases (Annali, 2022). The number rooms determine the size of a hotel; in this study, most of the respondents are small hotels, small hotels which are expected to have green practices towards sustainability with lesser costs or expense, however, the results showed that their is no significant relationship between the number of rooms in the hotels and its green practices. The results of this study emphasized that the size of the hotel or the number of rooms does not directly affect all the indicators for green practices of the hotels.

TABLE 3. SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP OF HOTEL PROFILE ALONG HOTELS GREEN PRACTICES

Indicators	No. of Rooms		Remarks
	Computed t	Tabulated at 5%	
1. Community Involvement and Development	1.73	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
2. Human Resource Management	.88	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
3. Consumer Issues and Protection	.99	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
4. Fair Operating Practices	.32	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
5. Environmental Health and Pollution	.48	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
6. Organizational Governance	1.34	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
7. Community Involvement and Development	0.5	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
8. Human Resource Management	1.81	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
9. Consumer Issues and Protection	.10	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
10. Fair Operating Practices	.52	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
11. Environmental Health and Pollution Prevention	2.06	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
12. Organizational Governance	.94	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
13. Community Involvement and Development	.17	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
14. Human Resource Management	2.49	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
15. Consumer Issues and Protection	.36	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
16. Fair Operating Practices	.17	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted

17. Environmental Health and Pollution Prevention	2.57	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted
18. Organization Governance	.98	1.96	H ₀ = Accepted

E. An Action Plan that promotes Greening Practices in Hotel Industry

To reach the goal of this study, which is to get hotels to use more green practices, an action plan is needed. It is a working document that could help the hotel industry keep track of how their government-mandated environmental policy goals are being made and carried out. The action plan contained strategies that could aid in the advancement of the hotel's sustainable practices in the future. In this case, information was given to meet the objectives. It also comprises potential programs, their accompanying goals, activities, concerned parties, and anticipated outcomes for each activity.

IV. CONCLUSION

On the basis of the data that was gathered, the researcher drawn the following conclusions:

- The profile of the hotel respondents in Albay varies in terms of no. of rooms, no of employees and years of operation. Most of the hotels who participated in the conduct of data gathering are considered as small hotels.
- The different green practices in terms of: community involvement and development, human resource management, consumer issues protection, fair operating practices, an organizational governance got the same adjectival interpretation of well-practiced. On the other hand, only the variable environmental health and pollution prevention got the adjectival interpretation of practiced.
- One of the difficulties faced by the hotels in Albay was the need for more funding to build and implement various green practices. While the respondents claim that the majority of the mentioned green practices are well-practiced, and the profile reveals that some of the hotels have been in operation for a while, it is difficult to secure money for their establishment and execution.
- Regarding the number of rooms and the hotel's green practices, the null hypothesis is accepted; therefore, there is no significant relationship. For the number of employees, only the variable environmental health and pollution prevention got a computed t of 2.06 with tabulated t at 5%, which indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant relationship. Lastly, for the years of operation, two of the variables got a rejected null hypothesis and have a significant relationship between the profile and the green practices: human resource management and environmental health and pollution prevention.

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